

Solitude is Bliss

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Nature's adjustment pays cold comfort -
With a breeze, exiled from the planet's equator.
No one around, yet it feels worthwhile -
With a canary's song and the murmur of mountain waves.

Who calls him a dawdler?
Or a trifler, idling in some comfort station?
If he finds joy in the forest -
Rather, call him a green panther.
Nature embraces him with an innate desire to create—as a dendrophile.

I agree with the Oracle of Solitude, as it whispers -
"Solitude is bliss."
That's why I never followed Cleisthenes' theory,
For it clings too tightly to worldly greed.
If the world ever ends up with economic tragedy,
Come, sit with me in the green courtyard.

More I have to offer -
The ethnic elegance of nature, where a church of love stands against a church of
hatred.
As war begins, a siren of valor assures the birds they need not fear.

Violence fells our thousand-year-old mother tree –
That embraces us in solitude, cuddles when in pain.

When dreaming, may the dream not turn to horror –
Instead, in the dream, a bed of roses may soothe the nerves.
The last minute of life, when the carriage takes us to death,
If nature offers cold comfort, it still feels worthwhile.

Death, for me, is the same occasion as birth –
With canary's melodious tone, I begin and stop with mountain waves.
A life I dream—in nature's green courtyard—trusting the Oracle of Solitude,
As it whispers: "Solitude is bliss."